

Exploring Tipping Points and Their
Impacts Using Earth System Models

Milestone 9

The toolbox for identifying emergent constraints has been developed

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MILESTONE REPORT

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Milestone	MS9 Toolbox for identifying emergent constraints has been developed
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1. Means of verification

This milestone marks the development of a comprehensive and statistically rigorous toolbox for identifying, quantifying, and interpreting emergent or observational constraints in climate projections. Observational constraints are statistical methods that integrate information from an ensemble of simulations across different climate models and available observations to better estimate future changes in a given variable and reduce the associated uncertainty. Such approaches are now considered in estimates delivered in IPCC reports.

To use such approaches within the TipESM project to reduce the estimate and uncertainty of future changes in the key tipping elements analysed, a toolbox has been developed. It has been named ClimLoco1.0 since it is the first version, but it might be further developed in the future. Its full description is provided in the published paper Portmann et al. (2025), which includes a Zenodo record of the associated Python code. The toolbox provides a unified framework for constraining projected climate variables using observational information, addressing long-standing limitations in the literature. Such limitations include inconsistent methodologies, incomplete treatment of uncertainty, and the lack of multivariate regression methods, which might allow the inclusion of various predictors representative of the different drivers that lead to the spread of the variable we are trying to constrain by observation. ClimLoco1.0 framework formalises emergent constraints as confidence intervals derived from statistical relationships between observable variables and projected climate responses. The toolbox is intended to support the application of observational constraints (naming preferred to “emergent constraints” since it is more in line with what the toolbox is actually doing) for different tipping elements.

2. About the work done to achieve this milestone

2.1 Objectives

The main objective of this milestone was to establish an operational and theoretically consistent framework for emergent constraints. This includes enabling statistically sound constrained projections with explicit uncertainty estimates, properly accounting for observational errors and internal variability. A further goal was to extend existing approaches to multivariate relationships, improve the treatment of finite ensemble sizes, and provide a basis for systematic comparison between different emergent constraint methodologies.

2.2 Synthesis of the main novelties implemented in ClimLoco1.0

A first key step was the formalisation of emergent constraints within a coherent statistical framework. Projected climate variables are treated as random variables estimated from ensembles of climate model simulations, clearly distinguishing between theoretical probability intervals and confidence intervals derived from finite samples. Indeed, from a statistical standpoint, using the term "prediction interval" is inappropriate for estimators, as is the case when considering simulations from an ensemble of models. A probability interval is a theoretical interval that would be obtained if the true ensemble mean and variance were known. In practice, these quantities must be estimated from a finite ensemble of models. The resulting interval, therefore, depends on the particular ensemble considered and may change as models are added or removed. In that sense, it should be interpreted as an estimate of the underlying probability interval, subject to sampling uncertainty. This clarification reveals that several approaches in the literature lack a fully consistent statistical interpretation, particularly in how uncertainty is propagated.

Building on this foundation, the ClimLoco1.0 framework was developed as the core of the toolbox. It is based on a linear regression formulation that links observable quantities to projected variables while explicitly accounting for sources of uncertainty, including regression error, ensemble size limitations, observational noise, and model-observation mismatches. The development followed a progressive pathway, moving from unconstrained projections to estimates with constraints based on noise-free observations, and finally to a complete formulation that included observational uncertainty. This stepwise approach improves transparency and helps isolate the contribution of each source of uncertainty.

A major advancement of the framework is the explicit representation of observational uncertainty, which is often simplified or ignored in existing studies. Measurement errors and internal variability are incorporated through a formal noise model, thereby defining a signal-to-noise ratio that quantifies the strength of emergent constraints. This treatment shows that neglecting observational uncertainty typically leads to overly strong inferred relationships and underestimation of projection uncertainty, while the proposed framework corrects for this bias.

The toolbox is further extended to multivariate constraints, enabling several observable variables to jointly inform projections. This extension reflects the inherently multivariate nature of climate dynamics and opens the possibility of improving predictive skill beyond traditional single-variable approaches. At the same time,

the framework highlights the risk of overfitting when the number of predictors becomes large relative to the available ensemble size.

Another important aspect of the work is quantifying the uncertainty associated with finite ensemble sizes. The analysis demonstrates that confidence intervals depend strongly on the number of climate models used, and that small ensembles can substantially underestimate uncertainty. Corrected formulations are introduced to ensure consistent propagation of sampling error and more robust inference.

Finally, the framework was benchmarked against commonly used emergent constraint approaches, including regression-based and probabilistic (Bayesian) methods, as well as approaches used in major assessment reports. This comparison shows that many existing methods can be interpreted within the proposed statistical structure and reveals inconsistencies in the treatment of uncertainty. The ClimLoco1.0 framework provides a unifying and more complete formulation. It is summarised in Fig. 1, coming from Portmann et al. (2025, their Fig. 10)

The toolbox has been implemented and tested through both synthetic experiments and real-world applications. These demonstrations illustrate how observational constraints, correlation strength, observational noise, and ensemble size affect constrained projections. The implementation is accompanied by reproducible code and graphical tools designed to support interpretation of regression relationships and uncertainty reduction: <https://zenodo.org/records/16742637>

3. Main outcomes

We have delivered a fully operational toolbox capable of producing statistically consistent constrained projections with explicit confidence intervals. It integrates observational uncertainty, supports multivariate constraints, and quantifies the impact of finite ensemble size. Importantly, it also improves the interpretability and comparability of emergent constraint approaches across studies.

Several key limitations in the current use of emergent constraints have been overcome, including methodological inconsistency, underestimation of uncertainty, and the limited exploitation of multivariate information. By providing a unified statistical framework, it improves the robustness and transparency of constrained climate projections and strengthens their relevance for climate assessments and decision-making contexts.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the effect of considering observational noise in a linear observational constraint (OC). (i) In red (non-bold), the observational noise is neglected. (ii) In green (bold), the observational noise is considered, which is more rigorous. The latter confidence interval (CI) corresponds to the statistical model ClimLoco1.0, presented in this article. (i) When observational noise is neglected, a linear relationship is defined between a past observable variable X and a future variable Y using an ensemble of climate models (black circles). The slope and error of the relationship between X and Y are shown as the red line and shading, respectively. A real-world observation of X is then fed into the linear relationship to obtain the CI of Y constrained (red interval, non-bold). Compared with the CI of Y unconstrained (black interval, with the large tails), the CI of constrained (red interval, non-bold) has a reduced uncertainty (interval width) and a corrected best guess (interval centre). The intensity of the best guess correction (between unconstrained and constrained) depends on the slope between X and Y and the difference between the multi-model mean and the observation (the “multi-model bias”). (ii) However, it does not take into account the uncertainty associated with the real-world observation. When taken into account, observational noise reduces the slope (green line, in bold) of the linear relationship and increases its error (green shading). Consequently, the CI of Y constrained by a noisy observation (green interval, bold) has less uncertainty reduction and a smaller best guess correction than the CI of Y constrained by a noiseless observation (red interval, non-bold). All three CIs use a 90 % confidence level.

4. Conclusions

This milestone establishes a comprehensive and theoretically grounded toolbox for emergent constraints, with ClimLoco1.0 as its central component. By combining rigorous statistical formulation, explicit treatment of uncertainty, and multivariate extensions, it provides a significant step forward in the methodology of constrained climate projections. The resulting framework offers a consistent basis for future developments and applications in climate science. Within the project, this framework will allow partners from Task 8.1 and the entire TipESM consortium to use the toolbox to develop emergent constraints for tipping elements analysed within the project.

5. Open Access

- The toolbox can be found here in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/16742637>
- The full paper describing the method in more detail has been published in open access: Portmann V., Chavent M., Swingedouw D. ClimLoco1.0: CLimate variable confidence Interval of Multivariate Linear Observational COncstraint *Geosc. Model Dev.*, [18\(22\)](#), pp. 9015-9038, 2025

6. Contribution to the TipESM objectives

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following project-specific objective (SO):

SO8	To deliver a risk register of future TPs and a set of safe emission pathways to minimise the chance of crossing such TPs through engagement with stakeholders and by feeding tailored information to adaptation strategies via ClimateAdapt and European Environmental Agency, European Climate and Health Observatory, ECDC, UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDDR), UNEP. KPIs: A risk register of the likelihood of crossing climate TPs and their consequences for climate, ecosystems and society; safe future emissions pathways sampled by the project ESMs. (Linked deliverables: D8.1, D8.2, D8.3. Linked milestones: MS9 , MS10)	Work packages: 1-7, 8, 9, and 10
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This toolbox enables the development of new observational constraints for key tipping elements, such as the AMOC. Applying these methods will improve the estimation of both the central tendency and the uncertainty of projected changes in these systems, thereby providing a more robust assessment of the risk of crossing critical thresholds. In this way, the results will directly contribute to and strengthen the tipping element risk register.